

MODELING 4-POINT BENDING OF THIN CARBON-EPOXY LAMINATES

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Abstract

A method for extracting and comparing the interlaminar stresses generated in carbon-epoxy thin laminates in four-point bending is presented. Computations were accomplished using three dimensional finite element models with commercial software packages StressCheck and ANSYS. The values of the induced interlaminar stresses for the four-point bending test show expected singularities at the free edge which require the development of a method for determining the region of valid results. The size of the singularity region is found using convergence studies of mesh refinement and element order (p-level). Although the maximum value of the induced interlaminar stress cannot be determined, relative comparisons can be performed between composite laminates with different angle ply layups to provide further insight into fatigue test results.

1. Introduction

Composite materials play an important role in improving the performance of advanced aerospace structures. However, the fatigue behavior of composite components can be difficult to predict. Previous studies show that the presence of interlaminar edge stresses [1] may cause delamination and subsequent failure in fatigue. A four-point bending test in fatigue may corroborate this hypothesis and validate the relationship between the fatigue behavior and the interlaminar stress in a composite laminate.

The classical laminate theory (CLT) can be used to determine in-plane stresses; but cannot predict the interlaminar stresses due to the plane stress assumptions of the CLT.

Interlaminar stresses (σ_z , τ_{xz} , τ_{yz}) occur near specimen edges due to the discontinuous change in the elastic material properties of the laminate plies [2]. The phenomena can be observed experimentally using the Moiré interferometry technique where studies have shown finite values of the interlaminar shear strains at the edges [3]. Finite element analysis (FEA) also provides a good alternative for predicting the interlaminar stress distributions throughout the laminate. Simulations have shown the presence of interlaminar stresses near the free edges at a distance equivalent to the thickness of the laminate [4, 5], as well as stress singularities at the ply interface and the free-edge. Studies using FEA illustrate that the accuracy of the interlaminar stresses near the edges is highly mesh dependent and the values tend to converge as they are evaluated away from the singularity area towards the centerline of the specimen [4].

Previous studies predicting interlaminar stresses have focused on axially loaded laminates [1, 3-6], but the interlaminar stress distributions from laminates in bending have not been extensively researched [7]. A four-point bending test could better represent the “in-service” loading conditions with combination of flexure, tensile and compressive loads.

The purpose of the current study is to develop a method for predicting the interlaminar stress distributions within bidirectional and angle-ply thin laminates in four-point bending. The commercial

packages ANSYS and StressCheck are used to develop consistent methods for model creation and result extraction.

The model description representing the four point bending test is described first, followed by preliminary results and a convergence study of the stresses near the free edges. The results of the interlaminar stress distributions are presented for the $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ carbon-epoxy thin laminates. The influence of fibre orientation on laminate response is investigated by comparing interlaminar stress results for laminates with different ply orientations.

2. Model description

The model representing the four-point bending test consisted of a simply supported 4-ply laminate with overall dimensions of 100 mm x 15.88 mm, as shown in Figure 1. Two line loads were applied across the width of the sample to theoretically produce a constant moment at the midspan and a longitudinal strain of 0.001 on the bottom surface of the laminate. The laminates considered in the analysis were a bidirectional $[0/90]_s$ and an angle ply $[\pm 45]_s$. Each ply had a thickness (h) equal to 0.1475 mm and was characterized as a homogenous elastic orthotropic material using the properties shown in Table 1.

2.1. Meshing and Modeling

In order to obtain the interlaminar stresses at the edges of the laminate, all plies were modeled with three-dimensional elements with elements concentrated at the edges and in the midspan where the values were extracted. The graded mesh is illustrated in Figure 2.

Two different approaches were used to mesh the models: In ANSYS, hexahedral elements with a quadratic polynomial function and three different mesh sizes were used. The number of elements across the width and through the thickness of each model is shown in Table 2.

In StressCheck, hexahedral elements with polynomial functions of degrees between 5 and 8 were used, and the number of elements through the

thickness varied from 2 to 16 elements per ply. As shown in Table 3, the degree of freedom (DOF) of each model depends on both the number of elements and the order of the polynomial function. This series of models was also used to define the size of the converged region.

3. Solution and preliminary results

Due to the small displacements involved and the absence of contact in the model, a linear analysis was performed. The values of the interlaminar stresses were extracted at the midspan of the specimen across the width of the laminate at the interface of the $\pm 45^\circ$ and the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ plies on the tension side ($z=-h$) of the specimen.

The values obtained for the interlaminar stresses in the $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ laminates in bending show the same trends as those reported from simulations of axial tensile loading [6] with the magnitude of the interlaminar stresses increasing at a distance of approximately the thickness of the laminate from the edge. For example, Figures 3 and 4 show the stress distribution across the width of a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate in tension and bending respectively. In both cases the values of the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} evaluated at the laminate centre line were equal to zero and the in-plane stresses (σ_x and τ_{xy}) corresponded to the analytical values obtained from the classical laminate theory. Near the free edge, within a distance of about one laminate thickness from the free edge ($y/b= 0.5$ for Figure 3 and $y/b= 0.925$ for Figure 4), the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} increased and the in-plane stresses showed a variation from the constant values in central region of the laminate. At the edge, the in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} tended to zero and the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} increased sharply to a maximum value. The values of the stresses shown in Figure 4 were converted to Psi and divided by the longitudinal strain (ϵ_1) in order to compare with the results in Figure 3.

Stress singularities were observed for the interlaminar stresses at the free edge in both $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ laminates in 4-point bending similar to the simulation of tension loading [5]. For example, as illustrated in Figure 5, the value of the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate

increased near the edge as the mesh was refined and the p-level increased. Although the magnitude of the interlaminar stresses near the edge increased as the DOF of the models increased, they tended to converge at a certain distance from the free edge.

3.1. Convergence Study

In order to define the size of the convergence region, the values of the interlaminar stresses obtained with StressCheck were compared between models using p-levels of 5 and 8. The values of the interlaminar stresses were considered to be converged when the difference using the two p-levels was less than 0.006 MPa. As shown in Figure 6, the difference in the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate for the model with 16 elements per ply was greater than 0.006 MPa at $y/b = 0.993$ or 0.05 mm from the edge, showing the beginning of the singularity region. The convergence area was similar for all the interlaminar stresses in the $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$, where the results for the two p-levels are in excellent agreement for $y/b = 0.993$.

The same observation, however, cannot be made for the 2 elements/ply model. Variations in the two p-level models appeared at $y/b = 0.8$, where the interlaminar stresses were negligible. This indicates that 2 elements through the thickness of a ply are not adequate to define the size of the convergence region where the interlaminar stresses are significant.

4. Interlaminar stress distribution in $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ laminates

The results for the interlaminar stress distributions in the $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ carbon-epoxy thin laminates in four-point bending are shown in Figures 7-8. The maximum values within converged region are listed in Table 4.

The interlaminar stresses in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate are shown in Figure 7 and are dominated by the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} . The presence of the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} begins at $y/b = 0.925$ which corresponds to a distance from the free edge equivalent to the thickness of the laminate. The

interlaminar shear stress τ_{yz} and the interlaminar normal stress σ_z are present in the laminate but their values at the boundary of the convergence region near the edge are small compared to the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} .

The overall values of the interlaminar stresses obtained for the $[0/90]_s$ laminate were smaller than the interlaminar stresses in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate. As shown in Figure 8, the interlaminar stress σ_z , begins at $y/b = 0.925$ in tension, changes to compression at $y/b = 0.985$ and reaches a maximum value as it approaches the free edge. The presence of the interlaminar shear stress τ_{yz} also begins at $y/b = 0.925$ with a maximum value near the edge and no interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} .

Table 4 shows that for both $[0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates the maximum of the interlaminar stress τ_{yz} and σ_z within converged region are relatively small compared to the interlaminar stress τ_{xz} in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate.

5. Influence of fibre orientation

The influence of fiber orientation on the interlaminar stresses was investigated by comparing laminates with plies oriented at 0° , 90° , 45° and 65° . Three different layups were evaluated: $[(0/90)_4]_s$, $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ and $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$.

The layups were determined in order to obtain a similar bending stiffness between each laminates. The $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminate was compared to $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate in order to evaluate the influence of the in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} on the interlaminar shear stress. Where, as shown in Figure 9, the in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} is lower in the $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminate than in the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate.

The values of the interlaminar stresses were evaluated through the thickness of the laminate at a distance of $y/b = 0.993$ or 0.05 mm from the edge which corresponds to the convergence area where the interlaminar stresses were significant. The results which characterize the influence of the fibre

orientation on the interlaminar stresses are shown in Figures 10 thru 12, and the values of the interlaminar stresses at the interface of each ply are listed in Table 5.

As shown in Figure 10, the overall magnitude of the interlaminar stresses in the $[(0/90)_4]_s$ laminate were smaller than for laminates with angle plies. In figure 11, the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate showed the largest interlaminar stresses with the maximum values of the interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} , and τ_{yz} occurring between the $45^\circ/90^\circ$ and the $90^\circ/-45^\circ$ plies. In figure 12, the interlaminar stresses in the $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminate showed the same trend as the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate ply with maximum values occurring between the angle plies and the 90° ply, although the magnitude of the stresses is reduced by almost 75% compared to the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate.

Table 5 shows the interlaminar stresses in the angle ply laminate are largest between the ply 2-3 and 3-4, which is correspond to the interface of the plies (45/90) and (90/-45) for the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate and (65/90) and (90/-65) for the $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminate.

6. Discussion

The present study of FEA models for laminates under four-point bending agrees with previous studies of FEA models for laminates under uniform axial extension [5]. In both cases the models showed interlaminar stresses near the edges at a distance corresponding to the thickness of the laminate and singularities at the edge but with a converged region when the values are extracted away from the edges.

Experimental studies on composite laminates show that finite values of interlaminar shear stresses exist at the edge [3]. The presence of stress singularities in FEA models is caused by the macroscopic representation of the laminate where each ply is represented by a homogenous elastic orthotropic material. In actuality, even though the properties of each ply are discontinuous, the matrix embedding

the fibers and bonding the plies together transfers the load to the adjacent ply and singularities do not occur.

Although the interlaminar stresses show a singularity in the FEA models, the current study demonstrates that the values of the interlaminar stresses of a thin laminate composite in four-point bending can be evaluated with confidence from a three dimensional model if the values are extracted in the convergence zone $y/b \leq 0.993$ or 0.05 mm from the edge for all layups considered in that study.

The convergence study showed that at least 16 higher order elements are required through the thickness of each ply in order to precisely define the size of the convergence region. Inside that region however, the results obtained for the interlaminar stresses are equivalent for all models used in this study independent of the number of elements through the thickness.

The behavior of the interlaminar stresses near the edges in a laminate can be explained by using the stress equilibrium equations from the theory of elasticity [4]. Consider a laminate loaded in 4-point bending, as shown in Figure 2. With a region removed from the areas of load introduction the stress components do not vary along the longitudinal direction (x -axis). In such regions the equilibrium equations take on a reduced form [4]:

$$\tau_{xz}(z) = - \int_{-h}^z \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} dz \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{yz}(z) = - \int_{-h}^z \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} dz \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_z(z) = - \int_{-h}^z \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} dz \quad (3)$$

The results for the interlaminar stress distributions in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate are dominated by the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} which is, from Equation (1), a function of the variation of the in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} across the width of the specimen. The absence of the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} in the

$[0/90]_s$ is consistent with the CLT that predicts no in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} in the laminate.

The study on the fiber orientations also shows that the in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} in the laminate has an important consequence on the interlaminar stresses. The $[(0/90)_4]_s$ laminate, which has no shear stress τ_{xy} , has the lowest interlaminar stresses. However, the shear stiffness of the laminate is 70% lower than the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate, and would not be recommended for most practical structural applications. The presence of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies in the laminate increases the shear stiffness but also produces significant interlaminar shear stresses between the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies. The $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminate has a shear stiffness 30% lower than the $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate but the maximum interlaminar stresses is reduced by more than 75%.

7. Conclusions

The values of the interlaminar stresses have been obtained for $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ laminates and show the presence of stress singularities at the intersection of the ply interface and the laminate edge. A convergence zone was defined as a region where increasing the degree of freedom of the model had no effect on the values obtained for the interlaminar stresses. The values taken at the interface inside the convergence region, show that the interlaminar stresses are higher in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate than in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate with the largest interlaminar shear stress being τ_{xz} . The methodology developed in this study allows thin laminate composites with different ply orientations under four-point bending to be compared in terms of their internal stress states. Although the maximum value of the interlaminar stress at the free edges cannot be precisely determined, relative comparisons can be made. For example, it is shown that by using a 65° ply instead of a 45° ply in a laminate the maximum interlaminar stress can be reduced by 75%.

8. References

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Table 1 - Material properties for carbon-epoxy -CYCOM 5276-1 with 640-800 tape

E_{11}	150 GPa
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	8 GPa
$G_{22} = G_{33} = G_{33}$	4 GPa
ν_{12}	0.25
ν_{23}	0.46
ν_{13}	0.30

Table 2 - ANSYS FEA models

Model	# Elements in transverse direction	# Elements through thickness of each ply	DOF
Coarse	60	5	797 838
Medium	75	5	871 152
Fine	75	10	2 536 653

Table 3 - StressCheck FEA models

Model	# Elements in transverse direction	# Elements through thickness of each ply	DOF
P-5	22	2	74 001
P-6	22	2	116 993
P-7	22	2	176 189
P-8	22	2	254 757
P-5	22	4	144 455
P-6	22	4	228 957
P-7	22	4	352 378
P-5	22	4	491 747
P-5	22	8	281 817
P-6	22	8	447 857
P-7	22	8	677 525
P-8	22	8	983 493
P-5	22	16	558 905
P-6	22	16	889 09
P-7	22	16	1 345 973
P-8	22	16	1 955 141

Table 4 - Maximum interlaminar stresses in convergence region for $[0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates.

	$[0/90]_s$ Laminate	$[\pm 45]_s$ Laminate
σ_z (MPa)	-0.3	-0.1
τ_{xz} (MPa)	0	3.5
τ_{yz} (MPa)	0.5	-0.9

Table 5 - Interlaminar stresses through the thickness at $y/b = 0.993$

	[[0/90] ₄] _s			[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0] _s			[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0] _s		
	σ_z (MPa)	τ_{xz} (MPa)	τ_{yz} (MPa)	σ_z (MPa)	τ_{xz} (MPa)	τ_{yz} (MPa)	σ_z (MPa)	τ_{xz} (MPa)	τ_{yz} (MPa)
Ply 1-2	0.34	0.00	-0.91	-0.39	1.14	1.13	0.05	0.18	-0.12
Ply 2-3	0.28	0.00	0.82	1.77	-5.84	-5.36	1.21	-1.22	-2.61
Ply 3-4	0.09	0.00	-0.57	1.41	-5.51	5.60	1.00	-1.14	2.64
Ply 4-5	0.07	0.00	0.50	-1.05	1.94	-0.97	-0.29	0.30	0.05
Ply 5-6	-0.01	0.00	-0.37	-0.84	1.88	0.59	-0.30	0.29	-0.10
Ply 6-7	0.03	0.00	0.24	0.68	-1.87	1.86	0.36	-0.39	0.88
Ply 7-8	-0.03	0.00	-0.14	-0.09	0.27	-0.19	-0.03	0.06	-0.02
Ply 8-9	-	-	-	0.00	0.21	-0.03	0.00	0.06	-0.04

Figure 1 - Laminate configuration, loading and boundary conditions (adapted from [4])

Figure 2 - Typical mesh for the laminate – ANSYS

Figure 3 - σ_z , τ_{xy} , τ_{xz} distribution along $\pm 45^\circ$ interface for a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate in tension.[6]

Figure 4 - σ_x , τ_{xy} , τ_{xz} distribution along $\pm 45^\circ$ interface for a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 5 - The τ_{xz} distributions along the width at the ply interface ($z = h$) for a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 6 - Differential values of τ_{xz} (p-8) and τ_{xz} (p-5) along the interface in $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 7 - Interlaminar stresses at the ply interface ($z = -h$) for a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 8 - Interlaminar stresses at the ply interface ($z = -h$) for a $[0/90]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 9 - In-plane stresses through the thickness for $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ and $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminates in 4-point bending

Figure 10 - Interlaminar stresses through the thickness at $y/b = 0.993$ for a $[(0/90)_4]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 11 - Interlaminar stresses through the thickness at $y/b = 0.993$ for a $[0/45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.

Figure 12 - Interlaminar stresses through the thickness at $y/b = 0.993$ for a $[0/65/90/-65/0/65/90/-65/0]_s$ laminate in 4-point bending.